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Orthopedic Supply and Auxiliary Means Applied to Disabled Child Staying at His Home Environment

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Abstract

The complex problems of the disabled children, the chances of their socialization and functioning in community have been investigated in connection with their families/tutors at their home environment. Physicians who are entitled to draw commissions for orthopedic supply are: orthopedist, surgeon, neurologist, rheumatologist, and ophthalmologist. The benefits of the good selection of the orthopedic supply and auxiliary means for the disabled child enable his optimal development and realization of his own plans that are so important for the uniquely able.

Keywords: disabled child, orthopedic supply, home environment

Introduction

The complex problems of the disabled children, the chances of their socialization and functioning in community have been investigated in connection with their families/tutors at their home environment [1].

Orthopedic Supply and Auxiliary Means

Disabled child staying at his home environment requires selection and application of the orthopedic supply and auxiliary means that are appropriate to his state of health and possibilities. The disabled person because of his state of health can benefit of the orthopedic supply and at the same time of the auxiliary means which are in full or in 70% refunded by the National Health Fund on the basis of the Ministry of Health Order on 17 December 2004 [2].

An appropriate selection of the orthopedic supply and auxiliary means depends on the decision of physician

treating the disabled child and on the present state of his health and psychophysical possibilities.

Physicians who are entitled to draw commissions for orthopedic supply are:

- orthopedist;
- surgeon;
- neurologist;
- rheumatologist;
- ophthalmologist.

On the other hand, the commissions for auxiliary means for the disabled children can be drawn by the following specialists:

- ophthalmologist;
- laryngologist;
- urologist;
- surgeon;
- orthopedist;
- neurologist;
- anaesthesiologist;
- pulmonologist;

- haematologist;
- doctor of basic health care;
- doctor of medical rehabilitation.

According to the Ministry of Health Order on 17 December 2004 there is a period of waiting for the specific orthopedic supply and auxiliary means. In order to improve the state of health and the comfort of living of the disabled child and his family tutors, it is possible to ask for shortening the period of utilization of the orthopedic articles.

The reason for shortening the waiting period for orthopedic articles for children and young people before 18 years of age is a noticeable change in their physical status which can result from:

1. Surgical procedures or some types of diseases.

2. Rehabilitation.

3. Physical development of the disabled child 4.

The application of the orthopedic supply and auxiliary means to the disabled child results from congenital or acquired diseases, injuries and also introduced and continued rehabilitation [3]. We present in Table 1 the overview of the orthopedic supply and auxiliary means that are most frequently employed in the disabled child staying at his home environment.

The appropriately chosen orthopedic supply and auxiliary aids together with implemented rehabilitation process facilitate vital functions of the small patient and in this way improve the comfort of his life at his home environment. They also allow the child to be the self-reliant in his family, among the boys of the same age and during and outside classes [4-6].

Table 1. The overview of the orthopedic supply and auxiliary means that are most frequently employed in the disabled child staying at his home environment.

No.	Medical indications	Orthopedic supply	Auxiliary means
1.	Amputations concerning lower limb	Prosthesis of lower limb Stump stockings	
2.	Amputations concerning upper limb	Prosthesis of upper limb limb Stump stockings	
3.	Scoliosis, permanent dysfunctions of the trunk	Orthopedic jackets	
4.	Paraplegia, quadriplegia		Antidecubital mattress Antidecubital pillow
5.	Congenital or permanent defects: abnormal position of the foot, shortening of the limb, paralysis and paresis, permanent contractions	Orthopedic footwear Orthopedic apparatus for upper and lower limbs	
6.	Permanent impairment of self-dependent movement	Walking sticks and crutches for permanent use	
7.	Infantile cerebral palsy	Special wheelchair stabilizing back and head Armchair	Nappy-panties Anatomical inserts
8.	Muscle paresis	Wheelchair for crawling on all fours	Urologic catheters
9.	Extensive paralysis and paresis of limbs and trunk	Individual devices for assuming vertical position	Nappy-panties Anatomical inserts
10.	Visual defects		Biconvex lenses Obturator Ocular prosthesis
11.	Hearing defects		Hearing aids Hearing supportive devices
12.	Cystic fibrosis		Nozzle inhaler

Conclusions

The benefits of the good selection of the orthopedic supply and auxiliary means for the disabled child enable his optimal development and realization of his own plans that are so important for the uniquely able.

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